

Joinson's Facebook Questionnaire: Italian adaptation and validation

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Abstract

Introduction: Studies on motivations and uses of social network sites (SNS), with particular reference to Facebook, have increasingly developed in the last decade. Nevertheless, there are still very few valid measures for Facebook activity, especially in Italian. The study aims to propose an Italian instrument, developed starting from Joinson's Facebook Questionnaire, and to verify its psychometric properties to provide researchers with a valid measure for the target population.

Methods: Three hundred fifty-five subjects, 185 males and 170 females, aged 9 to 45 years ($M = 23,14 \pm 6,22$), were individually interviewed with the Italian version of the Facebook Questionnaire.

Results: Exploratory factor analysis revealed a 7-factor latent structure, similar to the original study, which explained 52% of the variance and obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of .84. and different uses according to the life stage.

Conclusions: Methodological implications and cues for future research are discussed.

Take-home message: The Italian adaptation of Joinson's Facebook Questionnaire provides a reliable tool to explore social network usage across different life stages in Italy, demonstrating robust psychometric properties with a seven-factor structure that explains 52% of the variance and achieves a Cronbach's alpha of .84.

Keywords: facebook use; facebook questionnaire; measurement; psychological assessment; social networking sites.

INTRODUCTION

Several studies have focused on the psychological attitudes of social network sites (SNS) users, principally on Facebook. Most have studied the relationship between SNS use and personality or other psychological dimensions, raising some

contradictions [1,2]. It is well known that Facebook-related use is mediated by self-image, particularly self-presentational needs. Personality influences social media use, but the effects are unpredictable. Facebook activities and motivations correlate with agreeableness and extraversion [3]. Students with higher openness levels reported spending more time on Facebook and having more Facebook friends [4-6]. According to Ross et al. [7], extraversion and openness to experience would act as a motivation to communicate on SNS.

However, it must be highlighted that Facebook's use seems to correlate with traits of social introversion, loneliness, shyness [8], and even selfishness [9]. Despite Facebook users disclosing more information, they are not necessarily more satisfied with Facebook [10]. For example, stronger motivations to use Facebook to meet new people and enhance social inclusion predicted lower well-being among extroverts but higher well-being among introverts [11-13]. Moreover, other results showed an interaction between shyness and Facebook usage: individuals higher in shyness reported more robust associations between Facebook use and friendship quality than less shy individuals [14].

These assumptions lead to different inferences: first, it is not easy to determine the direction of the relationship between the use of Facebook and personality/psychological traits; secondly, if the use of Facebook is associated with opposite personality traits, this – in addition to the possible methodological obstacles – may also depend on the difficulty of objectifying the use of Facebook. It can be observed that when researchers consider psychological dimensions, such as personality, they employ validated measures supported by normative data and empirical studies [15,16].

On the contrary, most of the instruments utilized to measure Facebook activity or attitudes lack scientific evidence about the psychometric properties of the tools.

In most cases, the studies focused on Facebook consider almost exclusively quantitative variables, such as the time spent online, the number of friends, the frequency of posts, status updates, and friend's posts [17]. Other authors have developed specific measures to capture users' perceptions, beliefs, or attitudes without providing complete factor analyses, reliability, and validity tests to validate the instrument's psychometric properties [7-13]. The scientific consequence is the unavailability of valid instruments for researchers.

The increasing number of multinational and multicultural research projects has led to the need to translate and adapt Facebook measures. Based on the background, the present study aims to provide the psychometric properties of a Facebook Questionnaire, starting from the instrument developed by Joinson [18], to obtain a reliable tool for assessing Facebook motives and uses in the Italian language.

METHODS

Participants

Participated in the study 355 Italian-speaking individuals, 185 males and 170 females, aged from 9 to 45 years ($M = 23,14 \pm 6,22$). Subjects in the study group were stratified by the age interval into 5 subgroups: (1) below 18 years (14.6 %); (2) from 19 to 24 years (47.0 %); (3) from 25 to 29 years (15.8%); (4) from 30 to 35 years (14.6 %); (5) from 36 to 45 years (7.9 %). The educational level ranged from primary to postgraduate education. The most representative category was university students (61.1%).

Procedures and Measures

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Local Ethics Committee. All the subjects provided written informed consent, and minors were asked for their parents' permission to participate in the research. Participants were recruited from Southern Italy schools, university classes, and cultural associations. The face-to-face collective administration is required to last from 20 to 40 minutes. Data collection took place over six months. Joinson [18] initially developed the instruments in two phases. The first study was focused on three free-entry text questions about Facebook use spontaneously given by users, describing their Facebook use. The second study analyzed responses using an explorative

factor analysis (EFA). Results evidenced the presence of seven latent factors: (1) Social Connection (keeping in touch with friends); (2) Shared Identities (joining of groups, organizations, and events); (3) Photographs; (4) Content (5) Social Investigation; (6) Social Network Surfing (looking at other people's networks and friend); (7) Status updates.

In the present study, the questionnaire has been added to a broader set of questions which could be divided into 6 sections: (1) a sociodemographic questionnaire containing questions on gender, age, educational level, and city of provenience; (2) Facebook use: frequency, intensity and type of use; (3) activities conducted on Facebook, i.e. 28 yes/no items coded according the seven factors identified by Joinson; (4) two items related to the number of friends and the degree of relationship; (5) 6 items on privacy settings and self-disclosure; (6) a 5-point Likert scale (from 1 = strongly disagree, to 5 = strongly agree) investigating users' beliefs and attitudes towards Facebook.

Ethical aspects

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and has been approved by the Local Ethics Committee. All the subjects provided written informed consent after fully explaining the protocol design.

RESULTS

Statistics and data analysis

In order to explore the psychometric properties of the instrument, descriptive statistics, Cronbach's alpha, Pearson's correlation coefficient, and an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) were performed. Data were analyzed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences [19].

Table 1 shows descriptive statistics (Means and Standard Deviations) obtained by the sample for the five sub-groups divided by age groups. The Reliability scale analysis obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of .84. The Keiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) test for the sample adequacy was .82 with a p-value <.001. As reported in Table 1, younger users tend to prefer activities linked to Photographs (sharing, tags, etc.) [$\chi^2(4)=20.90$; $p<.001$] and show a higher motivation for Content gratification [$\chi^2(4)=10.05$; $p<.05$] and Social investigation [$\chi^2(4)=11.79$; $p<.01$]. Regarding gender, Photographs and Content activities prevail among females [PH $t(353)=-3.10$ $p<.005$; CO $t(353)=-5.58$, $p<.001$], whereas males are more interested in Social investigation [$t(353)=3.06$, $p<.005$].

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the sample according to age levels.

	<18 (N=52)		19-24 (N=167)		25-29 (N=56)		30-35 (N=52)		36-45 (N=28)	
Motives and uses of Facebook	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Social connection	.81	.31	.81	.30	.84	.28	.84	.32	.85	.22
Shared identities	.77	.44	.64	.41	.64	.44	.66	.46	.50	.35
Photographs	1.07	.50	.86	.45	.75	.44	.72	.52	.70	.48
Content	.83	.43	.77	.41	.69	.49	.76	.42	.54	.44
Social investigation	.49	.37	.41	.32	.32	.25	.37	.35	.30	.25
Social network surfing	.68	.50	.52	.41	.50	.41	.59	.46	.63	.55
Status update	.95	.51	.78	.45	.79	.54	.88	.51	.76	.41

The second step calculated correlations between Facebook use and motivation with Pearson's correlation coefficient. Table 2 shows that all components are strictly and positively related, such as the seven factors of the original questionnaire.

Table 2. Correlations between the 7 factors.

	SC	SI	PH	CO	SIN	SNS	SU
Social Connection	1						
Shared Identities	.129*	1					
Photographs	.227**	.461**	1				
Content	.154**	.296**	.404**	1			
Social Investigation	.299**	.361**	.414**	.187**	1		
Social Network Surfing	.138**	.357**	.453**	.307**	.465**	1	
Status Update	.269**	.384**	.509**	.356**	.296**	.327**	1

In this study, an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) with the extraction of eigenvalues greater than 1 and oblimin rotation with Keiser normalization was performed. As can be seen in Table 3, 7 factors were identified that were coherent with the original study. Overall, the seven factors explained 52% of the variance.

At least one of the aims of the study was to verify the connection between Facebook usage and the quantitative parameters mostly used in research, such as (1) time of registration, (2) frequency of log-in, (3) time spent online, (4) type of use (on-line vs. off-line). Pearson's correlation revealed that the time of registration and the type of use seems to be independent of the seven Facebook use factors. On the contrary, the frequency of log-in and the time spent online are positively related to all subscales [$p < .05$] except for Social connection (see Table 3).

Table 3. Factor structure of the Italian Facebook Questionnaire.

Factors	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<i>Essere taggato nelle foto</i> [Being tagged in photos]	.598						
<i>Entrare a far parte di gruppi</i> [Joining groups]	.569						
<i>Taggare le foto</i> [Tagging photos]	.559						
<i>Contattare amici che sono via da casa</i> [Contacting friends who are away from home]	-.549						
<i>Mettersi in comunicazione con persone con cui altrimenti avresti perso i contatti</i> [Reconnecting with people you've lost contact with]		.736					
<i>Trovare persone che non hai visto per un po' di tempo</i> [Finding people you haven't seen for a while]		.632					
<i>Mantenere relazioni con persone che non puoi vedere spesso</i> [Maintaining relationships with people you may not get to see very often]		.597					

<i>Tornare in contatto con persone che hai perso di vista</i> [Contacting friends who are away from home]	.494	
<i>Giocare</i> [Playing games]	.646	
<i>Scoprire applicazioni che vedi utilizzate dai tuoi amici</i> [Discovering apps because you see friends have added them]	.580	
<i>Compilare quiz</i> [Quizzes]	.570	
<i>Usare le applicazioni di Facebook</i> [Applications within Facebook]	.525	
<i>Guardare gli amici di altre persone</i> [Viewing other people's friends]	.770	
<i>Guardare profili di persone che non conosci</i> [Looking at the profiles of people you don't know]	.714	
<i>Dare un'occhiata agli amici dei tuoi amici</i> [Browsing your friends' friends]	.543	
<i>Ricevere richieste di amicizia</i> [Receiving a friend request]	.448	
<i>Perseguire altre persone</i> [Stalking other people]		-0.783
<i>Cercare specifiche tipologie di persone usando le funzioni di ricerca di Facebook</i> [Using advanced search to look for specific types of people]		-0.546
<i>Osservare virtualmente le persone</i> [Virtual people watching]		-0.378
<i>Vedere cosa stanno facendo attualmente i tuoi vecchi amici</i> [Finding out what old friends are doing now]		-0.728
<i>Aggiornare il tuo stato</i> [Updating your own status]		-0.545
<i>Condividere foto</i> [Sharing / posting photographs]		-0.529
<i>Guardare foto</i> [Viewing photos]		-0.487
<i>Vedere cosa le persone hanno scritto come stato</i> [Seeing what people have put as their status]		-0.405

<i>Leggere le "notizie"</i> [The news feed]	-400
<i>Organizzare o partecipare ad eventi</i> [Organizing or joining events]	.552
<i>Incontrare nuove persone</i> [Meeting new people]	.525
<i>Comunicare con persone con i tuoi stessi gusti</i> [Communication with likeminded people]	.397

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Social networking sites (SNS) have permeated our lives, and millions of subscribers worldwide are growing exponentially. Consequently, they have become increasingly crucial as objects of study. Current research in social and media psychology, in fact, is beginning to explore the individuals' use of SNS, such as Facebook and Twitter, with interesting results in terms of relationships with personality [1,6,12,20] and offline social behavior [14,21-25].

The present study aimed to explore the psychometric properties and the general validity of the instruments in the Italian language, starting from the one developed by Joinson [18] on Facebook user's motivations. In light of the International Test Commission (ITC) guidelines for the cross-cultural translation and adaptation of psychological instruments, results showed that the instrument is reliable and adequate to capture the differences related to age, underlying that motivations and uses of SNS change across the lifespan. Younger users prefer content-sharing gratification and use it linked to social investigation, as suggested by studies on the increase of social capital across the SNS [26].

Furthermore, the tool demonstrated sensitivity to gender differences. Female subjects, in fact, tend to use Facebook for photographs and content sharing, as if they had a tendency to self-exhibit [27]. Contrarily, the most important function performed by males, Social investigation, is presumably related to flirting purposes [28]. Findings suggest adequate validity and reliability values, encouraging the use of the instrument for the target population, and providing cues for future psychological and sociological research despite some limitations that must be pointed out.

There are many insights offered by the data obtained in this research. SNS gratification appears to be a pervasive phenomenon, a mass behavior that involves everyone, from children to the elderly. As has been emphasized, the study results cannot be generalized. Still, it was an excellent opportunity to test the sensitivity of a new instrument, which could be susceptible to changes. It should also be noted that: a) the formulation of some items could become more explicit and simple (for example, with regards to the perception of privacy risk); b) the Share Identity scale could be eliminated since it showed to measure a variable that weakly correlates at all with other uses; c) the sample could be better defined by creating several more homogeneous groups also by age.

Or, again, the study could be extended to other territories [29], probably even the demographic variables that produce differences in the uses and attitudes towards privacy.

Study limitations and implications for policymakers

This study is not without limitations. Having the necessary information to improve the tool could deepen the knowledge of the psychology of social networks by using this data in relation to psychological variables, such as personality characteristics or the relational dimension. Future studies should be focused on the differences between a use of "healthy" people and a use related to people with a pathological dependence on the Internet, as proposed by Caci et al. [30] with the "Facebook Addiction Italian Questionnaire."

The hypothesis remains that the work carried out has its own scientific dignity. However, it is placed in the descriptive context of research, and the latter should always be improved to serve the profession and the knowledge of the person and the society in which we live.

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